

Exchange Affinities for Alkaline Earth and Transition Metal Cations in a Synthetic Sodium Aluminosilicate Hydrogel

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Manuscript received 7 August 1987, revised 16 March 1988, accepted 25 April 1988

Cation exchange for several alkaline earth and transition metal ions in an amorphous sodium aluminosilicate hydrogel was carried out with isonormal solutions of these metallic chlorides and NaCl, and exchange affinities were compared by the standard Gibbs free energies determined with the application of simplified Gaines and Thomas equation. For the alkaline earth ions, exchange affinities were found to depend on the electrostatic field-strength of the hydrated ions and the enthalpy of ion hydration. For the transition metal ions, exchange affinities were influenced by the exchanger-phase entropy changes in some cases, and the affinity sequences agreed approximately with the order of stabilities of these metal chelates.

ION exchange affinity and selectivity in zeolites depend on electrostatic, steric, entropy, ion hydration, complex-formation, and lattice site factors¹⁻⁷. However, most of the works available in literature on exchange reactions involving zeolites have been carried out with crystalline hydrated aluminosilicate materials. The present investigation has been aimed at studying the exchange affinities of several alkaline earth and transition metal ions in an amorphous sodium aluminosilicate hydrogel exchanger.

Experimental

The amorphous cation-exchanger sodium aluminosilicate hydrogel $\text{Na}_2\text{O} \cdot \text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{SiO}_2 \cdot 5.1\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (which may be termed Na-exchanger) was prepared⁸ by wet interaction of sodium silicate and sodium aluminate, and its properties described in a previous study⁹. Exchange experiments and calculation were done following the methods employed by previous workers¹⁻⁵.

Cation exchange reaction was carried out by equilibrating 0.05 g of the Na-exchanger (50/100 mesh) with 50 ml of each of a series of mixed solutions containing varying proportions of NaCl and MCl, but with total electrolyte concentration being kept fixed at 0.02 N, where M=Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba, Mn, Ni, Co, Zn, Cd, Cu. Equilibrations were carried out in water-baths at 15, 30 and 45°.

The concentrations of M^{2+} cations were determined by EDTA titrations. The concentration of NaCl in the solution after exchange was calculated from the extent of exchange, taking into consideration that the total electrolyte concentration was always 0.02 N. Ion-exchange isotherms were plotted in the conventional way. Of all the cations, the

highest exchange levels were attained with Ba^{2+} , and these were used to calculate the maximum possible exchange capacities at the experimental temperatures which were required for calculation of normalised selectivity coefficients.

The cation exchange equilibrium for $\text{Na}^+/\text{M}^{2+}$ exchange may be expressed as

where, ex=exchanger phase and h=aqueous phase. The normalised selectivity coefficient ${}^N K_o$ is given by

$${}^N K_o = \frac{N_M m_{\text{Na}}^2 \gamma_{\text{NaCl}}^{\pm}}{(1 - N_M)^2 m_M \gamma_{\text{MCl}_2}^{\pm}}$$

Molarity was used in calculation in place of molality (m) as the solutions were very dilute. The mean activity coefficients (γ_{\pm}) were calculated with the help of Debye-Hückel equation as extended by Davies¹⁰. The term in the Davies equation standing for the constant A of Debye-Hückel equation was replaced by appropriate values of A according to the temperature of exchange study, taking data from Robinson and Stokes¹¹. The maximum ionic strength (0.03 M) of the exchange solutions used was well within the limit for which Davies equation is valid.

The thermodynamic equilibrium constant K was calculated from the simplified Gaines and Thomas¹² equation which, for the $\text{Na}^+/\text{M}^{2+}$ exchange, takes the form,

$$\log_{10} K = -0.4343 + \int_0^1 \log_{10} {}^N K_o dN_M$$

The standard Gibbs free energy change per equivalent of exchange reactions was calculated from the

equation,

$$\Delta G^\circ = (-RT \ln K)/2$$

as two equivalents are involved in the exchange reaction.

Reversibility tests were carried out by equilibrating the properly washed divalent metal-exchanged exchanger with 50 ml of 0.02 *N* NaCl solution, and determining the concentration of M^{2+} ion in the solution phase by EDTA, which established the reversible nature of the present exchange system.

Results and Discussion

Some of the exchange isotherms and Kielland plots are shown in Figs. 1 and 2. Thermodynamic equilibrium constants were calculated from the Kielland plots and ΔG° calculated from the equilibrium constants are given in Table 1. ΔH° values were calculated from the $\log K$ vs $1/T$ plots. Where

Fig. 1. Ion-exchange isotherms for some of the cations. E_M —equivalent fraction of entering cation in the exchanger phase, S_M —equivalent fraction of the same cation in the solution phase under equilibrium.

the plots were non-linear, the calculation was done from the slopes of the curves at 30°. ΔH° values for Ca and Cu were taken to be zero as their curves passed through extremum at 30°. Entropies of exchange at 30° were calculated from the relation, $\Delta G^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - T\Delta S^\circ$ (Table 1).

Fig. 2. Kielland plots for some of the cations. $N_M K_c$ —normalised selectivity coefficient, N_M —normalised equivalent fraction of entering cation in the exchanger phase under equilibrium.

For the purpose of thermodynamic analysis, the overall exchange reaction may be split into two stages, the solution-phase reaction and the exchanger-phase reaction^{1,2}. Consequently, the total standard enthalpy and entropy of exchange can be split up into their respective solution-phase (h) and exchanger-phase (ex) contributions according to the relations,

$$\Delta H^\circ = \Delta H_h^\circ + \Delta H_{ex}^\circ$$

$$\Delta S^\circ = \Delta S_h^\circ + \Delta S_{ex}^\circ$$

TABLE 1—STANDARD GIBBS FREE ENERGIES (CAL/EQUIV), ENTHALPIES (CAL/EQUIV) AND ENTROPIES (E U./EQUIV) FOR EXCHANGE REACTIONS FOR DIFFERENT ENTERING CATIONS

Cation (II)	ΔG° (15°)	ΔG° (30°)	ΔG° (45°)	ΔH° (30°)	ΔH_h° (30°)	ΔH_{so}° (30°)	ΔS° (30°)	ΔS_h° (30°)	ΔS_{so}° (30°)
Mg	+946	+869	+560	+8 007	+132 800	-124 793	+23.56	+10.95	+12.61
Ca	+186	+340	+174	0	+93 400	-93 400	-1.12	+4.20	-5.32
Sr	-124	-109	-66	-1 373	+75 750	-77 123	-4.17	+3.40	-7.57
Ba	-544	-452	-435	-3 090	+58 750	-61 840	-8.71	-1.95	-6.76
Zn	-342	-274	+122	-7 092	+147 400	-154 492	-22.50	+11.05	-33.55
Cd	-397	-340	-13	-5 948	+118 900	-124 848	-18.51	+6.40	-24.91
Mn	+80	+175	+525	-5 834	+123 600	-129 434	-19.84	+9.85	-29.69
Co	-207	-161	+80	-4 462	+145 650	-150 112	-14.20	+13.80	-28.00
Ni	+305	+367	+474	-2 675	+153 400	-156 075	-10.04	+15.00	-25.04
Cu	+204	-654	-163	0	+153 850	-153 850	+2.16	+10.75	-8.59

The solution-phase changes in enthalpy and entropy per equivalent of reaction were calculated from the reported data¹³, and from these, the exchanger-phase contributions were calculated using the above relations (Table 1). The overall exchange affinities have been compared from the values of ΔG° .

For the alkaline earth ions, it is seen from Table 1 that at each temperature of study, exchange affinity increases in the order, $Mg^{2+} < Ca^{2+} < Sr^{2+} < Ba^{2+}$. This sequence agrees with the electrostatic field-strengths of the hydrated ions as the hydrated size decreases along the series. From Table 1 the solution-phase enthalpy change (ΔH_h°) appears to be the controlling factor as it is most endothermic with Mg, and the endothermicity follows an inverse relation with the exchange affinity.

Fig. 3. Dependence of standard free energy of exchange on the enthalpy of hydration of ions.

The involvement of solution-phase enthalpy change indicates dehydration of the entering cation, which is confirmed from Fig. 3 showing exchange affinity to be directly related to the enthalpy of hydration of ions¹⁴. Stripping of hydration shell, therefore, appears to be an important factor controlling the exchange affinity, permitting penetration of the ions into the channels and cavities of the exchanger. This would account for the very high degree of exchange with Ba^{2+} possessing the smallest hydrated size. Regarding the entropy factor, it is seen from Table 1 that the changes in the entropy values do not explain the exchange affinity sequence.

For the divalent transition metal ions, the sequences of exchange affinity at different temperatures (Table 1) are as follows: $Ni < Cu < Mn < Co < Zn < Cd$ (15°), $Ni < Mn < Co < Zn < Cd < Cu$ (30°), $Mn < Ni < Zn < Co < Cd < Cu$ (45°).

The wide variation in exchange affinity cannot be primarily due to the size factor as the ionic sizes lie within a close range. The exchanger-phase enthalpies are all negative, and it is these exothermic quantities that counteract the endothermic solution-phase enthalpies to provide the main driving force for exchange in most of the cases.

On examining the enthalpy and entropy values with respect to the changes in ΔG° , it is found from Table 1 that the observed sequence of exchange affinities at 30° cannot be explained by ΔH_h° , ΔH_{so}° or ΔS_h° data, but can partly be explained by the ΔS_{so}° sequence. As ΔS_{so}° increases, the exchange affinity also increases in some cases, e.g. in the series Mn, Co, Cd, Cu.

Involvement of the exchanger-phase entropy indicates that chelation of the transition metal cations with the aluminosilicate framework oxygens may be a critical factor governing exchange affinity. For a large number of oxygen-donor ligands the average order of stabilities of divalent transition metal chelates¹⁵ in aqueous medium is $Mn < Co < Ni < Zn < Cd < Cu$. The sequences of exchange affinities observed in the present study agree

approximately with the chelate-stability order shown above, and to some extent with the results of previous workers⁵. However, it is likely that the rigidity of the aluminosilicate framework may impose some kind of steric constraints^{16,17} preventing adoption of the usual coordination by a cation. This structural factor, which would be present in solid chelating agents, has a great role in deciding the coordination behaviour. Consequently, the chelate-stability sequence of cations in solid exchangers may not follow the same trend as in aqueous solution. Another contributing factor for unusual coordination is the irregularity of the size and distribution of the pores in the amorphous aluminosilicate hydrogel structure. These may explain the irregularities of the observed affinity sequence in relation to that applicable in aqueous solution.

In the exchanger-phase reaction, the release of weak-field Na^+ ions would not lead to as much disordering as the ordering effect produced when the strong-field M^{2+} ions become fixed in the exchanger structure. Moreover, the rigidity of the aluminosilicate structure prevents full chelation at all the normal coordination positions of the cations. As a result, the residual field of these partially chelated cations would exert some structuring influence on the surrounding water molecules. These factors will lead to a negative contribution to the exchanger-phase entropy which may outweigh the positive contribution arising out of randomisation of water molecules⁸. This would explain the negative sign of ΔS_{ex}^0 and ΔS^0 . The negative entropies for Ca, Sr and Ba may likewise be due to the partial saturation of cationic coordination when the bonds are primarily electrostatic.

The unusually high affinity for Cu^{2+} may be due to the extra stability of Cu^{2+} -chelates conferred by Jahn-Teller effect. Evidences of such type of distortion and its favourable effect on exchange have been obtained with some cases of Cu-zeolites^{18,19}.

Another point is the comparatively high exchange affinity of Cd^{2+} . This d^{10} cation has no ligand field stabilisation energy, but still it forms strong chelate. It is probable that the ease of distortion of the filled d -shell²⁰ and the size of the ion¹⁵ may have a favourable influence on chelation.

The irregular temperature-variation of ΔG^0 for Ca and Cu appears unusual which cannot be explained with the existing data. It is seen that ΔG^0 values were positive in some cases, yet exchange reactions did occur, as found in some

other studies²¹. This is not contradictory because the actual reaction conditions were different from the standard state conditions.

Conclusion: Exchange affinities for alkaline earth ions in an amorphous sodium aluminosilicate hydrogel exchanger were found to follow a direct relation with the electrostatic field-strength of the hydrated ions. Exchange affinity increased from Mg^{2+} to Ba^{2+} along with increase of enthalpy of ion hydration, indicating that stripping of hydration shell of these ions is an important factor controlling the exchange affinity. Exchange affinities for the transition metal ions in the same hydrogel exchanger were found to be influenced by the exchanger-phase entropy changes in some cases. Results indicate that chelation of these metal ions with the aluminosilicate framework oxygens is a critical factor governing exchange affinity.

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